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Otters in Taiwan: The Situation of Distribution and Administration for *Lutra lutra* and *Aonyx cinerea* in Taiwan

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Abstract

The *Lutra lutra* is a protected animal in Taiwan. In the past, it was distributed in the shallow mountains of Taiwan's main island. However, since 1989, there has been no record on Taiwan's main island. Nowadays, there are only about 200 *Lutra lutra* on Kinmen Island. In the past five years, Japan-based regions have begun to upload images of otters on the Internet, arousing public attention to otters. In addition, Singapore, which is highly urbanized, has many wild *Lutra perspicillata* populations, which is also a different imagination of the relationship between otters and habitats. This study hopes to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the current situation for otters in Taiwan by integrating the distribution of otters in Taiwan, including both human-bred and wild individuals.

The wild *Lutra lutra* individuals in Taiwan are currently recorded on Kinmen Island, which is mainly managed by the Kinmen National Park, Endemic Species Research Institute, and Forestry Bureau of Council of Agriculture. In addition, the *Lutra lutra* wild tracking platform set up by Taiwan Biodiversity Network has been observed and recorded until 2022. There are currently only two artificially bred otters in Taiwan, "Taipei Zoo" and "Farglory Ocean Park", of which only "Taipei Zoo" has *Lutra lutra*, and *Aonyx cinerea* are breeding in both places. However, the *Aonyx cinerea* is not a native species in Taiwan, and current research shows that there is only a distribution history of *Lutra lutra* on Taiwan's main island. The administration of *Lutra lutra* includes existing conservation and restoration or the possibility of wild release in the future. For example, in California in the 1970s, the strategy of *Enhydra lutris* restoration and wild release was adopted, while the *Aonyx cinerea* in Taiwan is still mainly for the breeding direction.

Keywords: Otters, *Lutra lutra*, *Aonyx cinerea*, Distribution, Administration

